

projectEureka

A Gateway for Cloud and K8s HPC & AI Bursting

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Abstract—A demonstration of projectEureka and overview of its design and development. It is based on a new meta-scheduler, omni-scheduler, and is built for routing HPC and artificial intelligence jobs between Kubernetes (K8s), multicloud, and traditional HPC schedulers. projectEureka leverages this unified meta-scheduler for interactive application integration with Open OnDemand with a newly developed project-based user interface.

Keywords—HPC, Artificial Intelligence, AI, scheduling, Open OnDemand, Interactive Applications, Multicloud

I. INTRODUCTION

Drawing from our extensive experience in developing and maintaining CloudyCluster, we have encountered numerous scenarios where researchers and research computing support teams have articulated a need for enhanced integration between cloud-based and on-premises systems. This demand is accentuated by the ongoing expansion of computational workloads, which range from traditional batch High Performance Computing (HPC) and High Throughput Computing (HTC) to interactive computing, AI model training, and inference. These workloads span various platforms including Slurm clusters, Kubernetes clusters, and diverse cloud services, highlighting the critical need for tools that can streamline orchestration and usability of these complex environments.

To address this challenge, we initiated a project in January 2023 aimed at developing a system that tackles the following key problem areas in the current state-of-the-art: (1) Seamless cloud integration with on-premises systems, (2) Intelligent job routing between on-premises and multiple cloud accounts, (3) Integrated multi-point data staging between various cloud accounts and on-premises systems, and (4) A project-based user interface designed to simplify processes for researchers and support personnel.

In this paper, we discuss the design and development of a meta-scheduler-based system that incorporates these goals to provide a simple, secure layer for managing resources in a unified manner across both cloud and on-premises environments, as outlined in Fig 1.

Fig 1.

II. COMPONENTS

A. Meta-scheduler Core

The meta-scheduler will provide the core facility for managing jobs, job routing, multi-location resource provisioning, and simplifying the integration of core functionality, addressing the four key problem areas outlined in the introduction.

The core of the meta-scheduler architecture is built on Adaptive Framework (AFW)[1], which provides: (1) a JSON object store that surfaces a consistent interface for abstracted data-store access, (2) customizable rules-based authorization of object interactions, (3) internal and external event triggers based on object changes. Facilities have and will also be built around these to support: (4) an event driven data staging subsystem, (5) a comprehensive job language, and (6) an adaptable interface to support standard Slurm commands and additional job directives to provide access to the core capabilities.

As outlined in Fig 2, AFW provides a common interface to all the end user components, such as Open OnDemand[2], the Eureka project based user interface, and command line utilities, through https and leveraging JSON as the payload.

Fig 2.

These components, while authenticated as the end-user, reducing the risk of privilege escalation, can create objects that represent jobs directly into the meta-scheduler data-store. Authorization of this process is governed by the AFW rules that are put in place to securely restrict access to those previously given permissions within the object-store. Once the job object is created, an AFW event notification is sent to the meta-scheduler process which, based on the resource configuration, determines when and where the job should be executed. Once determined, the meta-scheduler will create the appropriate resource objects in the AFW-based data-store, triggering the resource creation in the respective provider. The providers will be either AWS, Google Cloud, Azure, Kubernetes (K8s), or in the case of job routing, it will forward the job to the designated slurm scheduler. When the meta-scheduler determines the resources from the provider are ready, an event-listener on the compute nodes will be notified of the job to be executed on the nodes. Whenever a job is marked completed it will cause an - to trigger the clean-up of the respective provider resources.

B. Multi-cloud Data Staging System

Seamlessly integrating data for research computing jobs is the third key area. Research data is expanding not only in size, but also in the number of storage locations. While there are tools such as Globus[3] that can help manage data between sites, within a site most users are left to leverage system utilities. After several months of attempting to use existing on-premises open tools for this, we determined that we needed to develop tools directly dedicated to on-premises multi-cloud data transfers.

A multi-point data transfer system, omni-copy (ocp), based on smart_open [4], has been developed to be leveraged by the meta-scheduler to handle data transfer as part of the job and resource provisioning process. As outlined above, the event driven process which translates jobs into the respective objects is core to how the meta-scheduler operates. An additional object-event that is built into the system is that of a data-transfer object. When a job script includes a transfer directive, it is translated into a data-transfer object that causes the specified data on a storage provider to be transferred to another location on its respective storage provider. The transfer will not initiate until all of the storage provider dependencies have been met,

will be performed as the user to significantly reduce the likelihood of privilege escalation, and once the transfer is complete, will mark the data-transfer object as complete so the clean-up process can start when appropriate.

C. Comprehensive Job Control Language

Research computing workloads have been shell script jobs for many decades, and there is a great amount of experience and existing knowledge and technical infrastructure to support these. To enable simplified adoption we are creating meta-scheduler job directives that can be added directly to existing jobs that will enable them to leverage projectEureka to allow for elastic resource provisioning and job routing. To achieve this goal we will be creating a language that will allow for existing shell scripts, that contain the new directives, to be transformed into the more comprehensive language that can support multiple cloud and processing parts.

This job control language, Omni Control Language (OCL), has been designed to be able to take new OCL job directives that can be added to traditional slurm scripts and translate them into native OCL, thus making the meta-scheduler have day-one value to researchers. On the other side, OCL is designed to provide more flexibility and capability with regard to extensibility and more complex jobs, including cross-provider capabilities within a single job. The directives will be in four parts: (1) computing resources that will be provisioned on demand as the job requires, (2) storage resources can be provisioned on demand as the job requires, (3) data staging can be configured to stage data and results at the appropriate time during the job, and (4) allow for multiple script executions that can interact with the provisioned resources and staged data.

D. Resource Provisioning Subsystem

The resource provisioning subsystem is the event-driven interface that creates and destroys resources used by the meta-scheduler, including clouds such as AWS, Google, Azure, and Kubernetes. In the initial development versions of projectEureka, we built an interface called Constellation that leveraged Terraform as the cloud interface. We found that Terraform lacked the parallelism needed for the dynamic nature of research computing jobs. Terraform also did not provide real-time interactive status of the resources that it provisioned. Terraform also was not implemented with the most efficient scalable cloud resource choices, such as bulk inserts on Google cloud.

Once a majority of the AFW event-based system was in place we looked to leverage the same capabilities of AFW to provide provisioning and deprovisioning of cloud resources. AFW has customizable extensions, and we are in the process of building these extensions that allow the meta-scheduler to interact natively with the cloud-provider and Kubernetes APIs. This will enable real-time interaction with the cloud provider control planes and direct adaptive interaction with the cloud resources. Job routing between provisioned and existing systems will be handled based on events as well. The

interaction between the meta-scheduler and the resource will happen through a similar interface leveraging this AFW capability.

E. Project Centric User Interface (UI)

To simplify data access and interactive application launching capabilities, a project-based user interface was developed to allow project leads and members to share common project data sources and common applications. This project interface provides a common way to access self-service resources. The associated data locations can also be referenced for data staging activities mentioned previously.

The project-centric UI is built using Vue and UI5 web components. The overarching project overview page from the user interface can be seen in the screenshot in Fig 3.

Fig 3.

An example of the running applications in a project is shown in the screenshot in Fig 4

Fig 4.

F. Multi-cloud Storage Management User Interface (UI)

The storage manager UI provides a project-based view of the directories and files associated with a project so members can easily manually manage files as required between the various storage locations residing in different clouds and on-premise resources.

The data staging system is abstracted both from the UI and scheduler, allowing for common code and key management for the data transfer operations of data and results staging. The system allows for directory traversal and listing across multiple clouds and local resources in an extensible fashion, where it can easily be extended to support additional storage locations

as outlined in Fig 1. An example of the storage manager UI is in Fig 5. This UI provides drag and drop support across multiple cloud and local storage resources. The storage manager UI leverages OCP outlined earlier.

Fig 5.

III. COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT

Throughout the months of developing projectEureka we have engaged with various communities to determine its usefulness and are tailoring it to meet the needs therein. We have had various meetings with potential communities in the US, EU, Japan, Singapore, and Australia; all have been met with positive feedback and significant interest in testing the system when available. The testing is scheduled to begin in the fall.

To address usability from a student community, we have participated in targeted ADMI and HPC in the City, SC23 hackathons. The system, projectEureka, was the main development collaboration system used in these hackathons, providing valuable usability feedback. As an example, the interactive job portion of the UI had previously launched separate cards from the launchers during application startup. After a majority of the 40 participants launched the same card multiple times we decided to have the main card transition to the running card and give another menu option to launch additional ones. We tested the changes during a design-safe hackathon with Texas Advanced Computing Center and it was much more user friendly.

To directly support the various research and education communities, the base of this project will be made free of charge with the option for paid support. We hope that this will provide a cross cloud and on-prem interconnectivity foundation for batch jobs, interactive virtual scientific workstations, and data staging that can be built upon.

As the final weeks of development approach on the v1 beta of this project, we have a list of users from various states and countries and different types of institutions, from technical schools to national centers, that will be deploying projectEureka to test, evaluate, and give feedback. Through this process we will iterate through the suggestions and incorporate ideas based on the feedback.

IV. RELATED WORK

One of the concepts that is key to reducing costs of federated cloud infrastructure is to have a zero-cost footprint in the cloud as outlined in the Eric Lam Tapis paper [5].

REFERENCES

- [1] Grieshop, Gossett, Adaptive Framework Open Source Project, <https://afw.tools>.
- [2] Hudak et al., (2018). Open OnDemand: A web-based client portal for HPC centers. *Journal of Open Source Software*, 3(25), 622, <https://doi.org/10.21105/joss.00622>.
- [3] Foster, I., "Globus Online: Accelerating and Democratizing Science through Cloud-Based Services," *Internet Computing, IEEE* , vol. 15, no. 3, pp. 70,73, May-June 2011
- [4] Radim Řehůřek et al., (2014), Smart Open - utils for streaming large files in Python, https://github.com/piskvorky/smart_open
- [5] Lam, Eric, et al. "Extending Tapis Workflow Management Framework with Elastic Google Cloud Distributed System using CloudyCluster by Omnibond." *Science Gateways 2022* (2022).
- [6] B. Posey et al., "On-Demand Urgent High Performance Computing Utilizing the Google Cloud Platform," *2019 IEEE/ACM HPC for Urgent Decision Making (UrgentHPC)*, Denver, CO, USA, 2019, pp. 13-23, doi: 10.1109/UrgentHPC49580.2019.00008.
- [7] B. Posey, et al., *Dynamic HPC clusters within amazon web services (aws)*. Diss. Clemson University, 2016